

MODERN APPROACHES TO STIMULATING THE DEVELOPMENT OF TERRITORIAL COMMUNITIES

Koroliak O.O.

Postgraduate Student of the Department
of Regional and Local Development
Institute of Administration, Public Governance,
and Professional Development
National University "Lviv Polytechnic"

***Abstract.** The article examines modern approaches to stimulating the development of territorial communities in Ukraine in the context of challenges and consequences of military actions. It is determined that one of the key prerequisites for intensive development of territories is the creation of local development institutions (LDI). The experience of Central and Eastern European countries, where the creation of LDI contributed to effective economic development, is studied. The main functions of LDI include providing consultations and support to enterprises, conducting economic research, project management, and promoting investment. Special attention is paid to EU programs such as LEADER, Horizon Europe, and the European Regional Development Fund, which can be adapted to Ukrainian realities. The positive experience of international programs, such as WWOOF, which contribute to the sustainable development of communities, is also considered. Despite significant potential, the existing local development institutions in Ukraine have not yet reached the quality level to become significant subjects of the organizational structure of local economic development management. The organizational and legal forms of LDI used in Ukraine indicate that the existing institutions are mainly representatives of the interests of one local interest group, and there are no examples*

of institutions created on the basis of partnership of all sectors: local authorities, businesses, and the public. The development of territorial communities with the implementation of LDI is a promising direction for achieving sustainable development and preserving Ukraine's natural resources. The implementation of the above-mentioned approaches and models will help increase economic potential, improve the well-being of residents, increase the attractiveness of communities for tourists, and contribute to the sustainable development of the country as a whole. In addition, the development of entrepreneurial initiative could significantly improve financial flows to territorial communities. However, the current mechanisms for encouraging entrepreneurship in the country do not effectively fulfill their main mission. The reason for this is a number of factors that hinder the development of entrepreneurship, including: the lack of motivational tools in state programs for creating own businesses; shortcomings in legislation and the system of state support for small businesses; distrust in the banking system; high tax rates and complexities in their administration; limited access to information and consulting support for small enterprises; issues with transparency and financial management; complicated relationships with regulatory bodies; lack of business management skills; deficiencies in strategic planning; limited access to capital and ineffective control of financial operations. Thus, the implementation of modern approaches to stimulating the development of territorial communities, taking into account the best international practices, is an important step towards ensuring sustainable economic development and improving the quality of life for residents of Ukraine. This will ensure the comprehensive development of territories and create conditions for the prosperity of communities.

Keywords: *Local community development, sustainable development, financial instruments, regional development, financial stimulation, budgetary decentralization.*

Formulation of the problem. The development of territorial communities is a key element of the economic and social growth of any country. In Ukraine, especially

in the context of current challenges and the consequences of military actions, the issue of stimulating the development of local communities has gained critical importance. Following the devastating consequences of conflicts, the country faces the task of restoring and modernizing infrastructure, creating new jobs, and improving the well-being of the population. For Ukraine, the development and implementation of a state regional policy aimed at reducing territorial disparities in socio-economic development and ensuring the financial viability of territorial communities are highly relevant today. This policy will contribute to their effective development. One of the main challenges remains the insufficient coordination between central and local authorities, as well as the absence of a unified strategic plan that would consolidate all initiatives and efforts. The need for a comprehensive approach to solving the problems of territorial communities is evident, as it will not only restore the destroyed infrastructure but also create conditions for sustainable development in the future. The relevance of researching modern approaches to stimulating the development of territorial communities in Ukraine is also determined by the need to address complex tasks related to financial support and economic growth of regions, improving and gradually achieving corresponding European and global standards of living for the population.

Analysis of recent research and publications. Questions of stimulating the development of territorial communities have been studied by domestic scientists such as Y. Barsky, T. Bezverkhnyuk, O. Vasylyk, G. Voznyak, Z. Herasymchuk, S. Doroguntsov, Y. Zhalilo, V. Zaychykova, O. Kyrylenko, I. Kaminska, M. Kuzhelev, I. Lunina, L. Makarenko, V. Melnyk, V. Oparin, Y. Ostrishchenko, V. Pylypiv, V. Polishchuk, S. Slukhai, O. Sontsova, L. Tarangul, I. Chugunov, and others. Among foreign scientists who have made significant contributions to the study of this issue are M. Bell, D. Bogolyepov, B. Weingast, A. Granberg, R. Musgrave, W. Oates, J. Rizza, J. Rodden, S. Rose-Ackerman, D. Swenson, C. Tiebout, and others.

The purpose and objectives of the article. This article aims to identify modern approaches to stimulating the development of territorial communities in

Ukraine and assess their effectiveness. The main tasks are: analyzing existing methods and programs aimed at the development of territorial communities, identifying the main obstacles and challenges to the implementation of these programs, evaluating the role of public organizations and international donors in supporting local development, developing recommendations for improving strategies to stimulate the development of territorial communities.

Main text. Among the key areas for the development of modern society is the enhancement of the role of local governance and the provision of necessary resources for the development of territorial communities. The development of a specific territory occurs under the influence of many factors, and among the existing models and approaches to the development of territorial communities, the following can be highlighted: sustainable development - this approach aims to meet the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs. Collaborative Development - emphasizes the involvement of community members in decision-making processes. It expands opportunities for local residents to take responsibility for their development through active participation in the planning, implementation, and monitoring of projects. Decentralization and local governance - involves the transfer of powers and resources from central to local authorities to increase efficiency and responsiveness to local needs. This model promotes local autonomy and encourages decision-making at the community level. Public-Private Partnership (PPP) - involves collaboration between public institutions and private sector companies to finance, construct, and operate projects such as infrastructure, healthcare, and education. PPPs aim to leverage the strengths of both sectors for community development [1]. Smart Cities and Digitalization - utilizes technology to improve the efficiency of urban services and meet the needs of residents. This includes integrating information and communication technologies into various aspects of city management and service delivery. Community-Based Natural Resource Management (CBNRM) - this model focuses on the sustainable management of natural resources, such as forests, fisheries, and wildlife, by the

communities living closest to them. It relies on local knowledge and practices to conserve resources while benefiting the local population [2]. Rural Development Models - these are designed to address the unique challenges of rural areas, including agricultural development, infrastructure improvement, and access to services. This often involves strategies to enhance agricultural productivity, market access, and livelihoods in rural areas. Urban Renewal and Revitalization - focuses on rejuvenating declining urban areas, improving physical infrastructure, housing, and public spaces. It often includes social and economic development initiatives. Integrated Regional Development - involves comprehensive planning and development that considers various aspects of a region – economic, social, environmental, and cultural – to create balanced and sustainable growth. Social Innovation and social entrepreneurship - encourages innovative solutions to social problems and needs, often through social enterprises that balance profit with social goals. In the EU, there are various programs that stimulate the sustainable development of territorial communities. Let's consider the most relevant ones for Ukraine. LEADER (an acronym for “Liaison Entre Actions de Développement de l'Économie Rurale” which means “Links between actions for the development of the rural economy”) is an approach that is an integral part of and funded by the investment component of the EU's Common Agricultural Policy. It is implemented within the national and regional rural development programs of each EU member state. The idea behind LEADER is to harness the energy and resources of people and local organizations as development actors, rather than beneficiaries, by empowering them to contribute to the future development of their rural areas through the formation of local action groups – partnerships between public, private, and community sectors (supporting rural communities in developing local strategies and financing projects that promote long-term socio-economic development). The success of LEADER in rural areas has encouraged the application of this approach in other types of territories. For this broader application, the term "Community-Led Local Development" (CLLD) is now used [7]. European Fund for Regional Development

(EFRD) aims to strengthen economic and social cohesion by correcting imbalances between regions. It supports the development of urban and rural communities, focusing on innovation, small and medium-sized enterprises, and green infrastructure [8]. Horizon Europe is the EU's key funding program for research and innovation, which includes initiatives aimed at developing new technologies that can be used to improve the infrastructure of territorial communities, as well as ensuring access to new markets. An example of a successful program for managing the sustainable development of territorial communities is "WWOOF" (World Wide Opportunities on Organic Farms). This global network promotes the exchange of volunteers who wish to learn and help on environmentally-oriented farms around the world. The listed international programs are examples of stimulating the development of territorial communities, providing the financial, technical, and advisory support necessary for the effective implementation of local initiatives. Programs such as LEADER, the European Fund for Regional Development (EFRD), Horizon Europe, and WWOOF offer relevant experience in how such efforts can be successfully implemented in practice in Ukraine. Depending on the level of recipient involvement in the implementation of the corresponding international technical assistance program or project, the following forms are distinguished: Technological grant - this involves the donor providing the recipient with technologies, goods, or financial resources free of charge, as well as the development of human resources or institutions without the recipient's participation in financing the project. In this case, the recipient's functions are limited to organizational activities to ensure the receipt of the relevant international technical assistance resources. Co-financing grant - this type of grant involves the recipient's participation not only in the organization but also in the financing of the activities specified by the project. Depending on the conditions of the assistance, the recipient's share usually ranges from 10% to 50% and can be provided in both monetary and in-kind forms, such as the use of premises, employee work hours, etc. The advantages include: an effective tool for attracting necessary resources (funds, equipment, and services) for local economic development needs,

the gratuity and non-repayable nature of international technical assistance resources for local economic development, reduction of time needed to acquire new knowledge and experience through professional consultations, gaining experience in preparing project applications and managing international technical assistance projects, which improves municipal management, exemption from taxation of resources received by the recipient within the framework of an international technical assistance project (program), the possibility of expanding the range of services provided in the community through infrastructure development.

The disadvantages include: development of "dependent" attitudes among recipients of international technical assistance, excessive focus on cooperation with international technical assistance projects (programs), the complexity and length of the procedures for selecting project proposals (cooperation proposals), the necessity of an adequate level of qualifications for officials to attract international technical assistance and implement relevant projects, the requirement to submit periodic reports on the status of implementation and results of the international technical assistance project (program), the risk of misjudging the need for new services, expected economic, and social effects. The activation of entrepreneurial initiative in Ukraine could significantly improve financial flows to territorial communities. However, the current mechanisms for encouraging entrepreneurship in the country do not effectively fulfill their main mission. This inefficiency is caused by a number of factors that hinder the development of entrepreneurship. Among them are: lack of motivational tools in state programs for creating own businesses, deficiencies in legislation and the state support system for small businesses, distrust in the local banking system and the absence of property guarantees, high tax rates and the complexity of their administration, limited access to informational and consultative support for small enterprises. issues with transparency and financial management, difficult relations with regulatory bodies, lack of business management skills, deficiencies in strategic planning, limited access to capital and ineffective control of financial operations, poor placement of business structures, among other problems.

One of the key prerequisites for intensive territorial development in the modern world is the establishment of Local Development Institutions (LDIs). The creation of LDIs has become widespread in Central and Eastern European countries, including Bulgaria, Estonia, Poland, the Czech Republic, and Hungary. The active process of founding these institutions began in the 1990s, coinciding with administrative-territorial reforms, the development of local self-government institutions, and the formulation of regional and local development policies. European integration processes also influenced the direction of LDI activities and their resource support. Access to EU structural funds and other support programs has enabled LDIs to strengthen organizationally and expand their scope of activities. A common trend in many countries recently is the creation of LDIs through partnerships between public authorities and the private sector, including entrepreneurs and the public. This approach allows for coordinated interventions in the local economy and ensures balanced territorial development. The most common functions of LDIs include: providing consulting and support to existing businesses, offering consulting and support during company formation, conducting economic or sectoral research, creating and maintaining databases of local companies, managing a database of available land plots and buildings, developing a database of available support tools for businesses, advising businesses on participating in trade fairs and shows, providing consultations on property transfers, ownership changes, and business cooperations, restructuring problematic enterprises, consulting territorial communities. Key elements that define the concept of "territorial economic development" and essential characteristics of LDIs include: Consideration of local context: LDI activities are aimed at maximizing the engagement of internal territorial potential for optimal use of local resources, taking into account the priorities of national development policies. Economic focus: LDIs are intended to promote economic development by supporting entrepreneurial initiatives and facilitating entrepreneurs' access to markets. Development orientation: The goal of LDI activities includes improving the quality of life for residents of the relevant territory by

promoting the creation of new jobs, increasing production volumes and income, strengthening social capital, etc.

Regarding legal support Municipal Enterprises Utility Companies, and Communal Organizations as potential forms of LDIs are part of the communal property rights of territorial communities and an element of the local self-government system. The legal status, establishment procedures, activities, and powers of local self-government bodies concerning the creation, financing, regulation, and control of their activities are comprehensively regulated by the Law of Ukraine "On Local Self-Government in Ukraine" and the Commercial Code of Ukraine (GKU). The commercial legislation classifies municipal enterprises as a distinct type and organizational form of enterprises (Article 63 GKU), determines the composition of enterprise property and sources of its formation (Article 66 GKU), specifics of the creation and functioning of communal unitary enterprises (Article 78 GKU), and establishes the specifics of exercising the right of economic management (Article 136 GKU) and the right of operational management (Article 137 GKU). The activities of utility companies are regulated by provisions regarding non-commercial economic activities and the right of economic management (Articles 52-54, Article 136 GKU) in the commercial legislation. Legal status, formation (registration), functioning, and activities of public associations and charitable organizations, in the form of which LDIs can be created, are determined by special legislation – the Law of Ukraine "On Public Associations" and the Law of Ukraine "On Charitable Activities and Charitable Organizations." The taxation procedure for these non-profit organizations is regulated by tax legislation (Article 133 of the Tax Code of Ukraine). In 2014, within the framework of the "Local Economic Development" project, a catalog of existing LDIs in Ukraine was prepared and published. The review indicates that most of them were created in the form of public associations (38 out of 58 analyzed institutions). Ten LDIs were created in the form of municipal enterprises, and five in the form of utility companies; four institutions operate as charitable organizations (mostly focusing on solving social problems in the respective territories), and only

one institution was created in the form of a commercial enterprise. This indicates greater activity in the creation of local development institutions by the public sector as opposed to public authorities.

Conclusions and perspectives of further development. The summary of foreign experience leads to the conclusion that a powerful incentive for the creation of local development institutions (LDIs) was primarily the realization by local authorities of the necessity to apply new approaches to ensuring the economic development of territorial communities and the recognition of the need to create specialized institutions capable of implementing these new approaches in practice. The main tasks that LDIs set for themselves today in Ukraine include: improving the quality of strategic management of territorial community development, sustainable economic development of territorial communities, managing the implementation of specific projects, conducting social and marketing research, promotion and branding of territories, facilitating investment attraction, supporting the development of local businesses, solving social problems of territorial communities, and more. At the same time, the existing LDIs have not yet achieved the qualitative level to become significant entities within the organizational structure of local economic development management. The organizational and legal forms of LDIs used in Ukraine indicate that existing institutions are mainly representatives of the interests of a single local interest group, and there are no examples of institutions created on the basis of partnerships across all sectors: local authorities, business, and the community. The development of territorial communities with the implementation of LDIs is a promising direction for achieving sustainable development and preserving Ukraine's natural resources. Implementing the above-mentioned approaches and models will help increase economic potential, improve the well-being of residents, enhance the attractiveness of communities for tourists, and promote the sustainable development of the country as a whole.

References:

1. Slobozhan O.V. "Models of Local Economic Development," Kyiv 2019. 140 pages
2. Law of Ukraine "On Public Associations" dated 22.03.2012 No. 4572-VI
3. Law of Ukraine "On Local Self-Government in Ukraine" dated 21.05.1997 No. 280/97-VR (Articles 1, 5, 11, 26–40, 54)
4. Law of Ukraine "On Local Self-Government in Ukraine" dated 21.05.1997 No. 280/97-VR (Subparagraphs 29, 30, and 32 of Part 1 of Article 26, Subparagraph 6 of Paragraph "a" of Article 28, Subparagraph 2 of Paragraph "a" of Article 29, Parts 1 and 3 of Article 60)
5. URL: <https://rpr.org.ua/news/derzhavna-rehionalna-polityka-2023-buty-chy-ne-buty/>
6. I.V. Kotov "Problems of Public Management of Sustainable Development of Territorial Communities in the Context of Crisis Situations," Investments: Practice and Experience, 2023, No. 18, pp. 216-220.
7. On the Approval of the Concept of Sustainable Development of Human Settlements: Resolution of the Verkhovna Rada of Ukraine dated December 24, 1999 No. 1359-XIV. URL: <http://zakon3.rada.gov.Ua/laws/show/1359'14>.
8. Resolution dated August 5, 2020, No. 695 "State Strategy for Regional Development for 2021-2027"
9. Employment Opportunities for Youth in the Field of Green Tourism: Methodological Recommendations for Starting Own Business / [Ed. O.V. Kulinich]. Kharkiv: Institute of Regional Social Policy, 2011. - p. 124.
10. I.V. Kotov "Problems of Public Management of Sustainable Development of Territorial Communities in the Context of Crisis Situations" URL: <https://dspace.chmnu.edu.ua/jspui/bitstream/123456789/1351/1/2023.%20-%20%E2%84%96%2018.pdf#page=217>

11. On the Approval of the Concept of Sustainable Development of Human Settlements: Resolution of the Verkhovna Rada of Ukraine dated December 24, 1999 No. 1359-XIV.

12. Romanyuk I.A. "Development of Entrepreneurship and Alternative Types of Activities for Rural Population" / Economics. Management. Business. - 2014. No. 1. pp. 117-122.

13. Territorial Community Amalgamation as a Mechanism for Ensuring Resource Capability of Rural Communities / S.I. Chernov, N.Yu. Mushchynska // Theory and Practice of Public Administration. - 2016. - Issue 3. - pp. 172-177.

14. Sheiko Yu.O. "Stimulating the Development of Small Entrepreneurship in the Region"

URL: <https://lib.lntu.edu.ua/sites/default/files/2021-01/%D0%B0%D0%B2%D1%82%D0%BE%D1%80%D0%B5%D1%84.%20%D0%A8%D0%B5%D0%B9%D0%BA%D0%BE%20%D0%AE.%D0%9E.pdf>